

A validated HPLC method for simultaneous determination of four active components in counter cough formulation

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Abstract : A new quantitative reversed-phase HPLC method has been developed for the simultaneous determination of phenylephrine hydrochloride (PEH), guaiphenesin (GP), ambroxol hydrochloride (AMBH) and levocetirizine dihydrochloride (LCZH) in counter cough formulation. Mobile phase consists of phosphate buffer of pH 3.0 and solvent mixture (methanol : acetonitrile in the ratio of 1 : 2) using gradient system. Column reversed phase Luna C₈ (5 μm, 250 × 4.6 mm i.d.) phenomenex is used as stationary phase. The elution of analytes is achieved in less than 30 min with a flow rate of 1.0 ml min⁻¹. Detection is carried out using a variable wavelength UV-Vis detector at 273 nm and 230 nm. Linearity and percent recoveries for PEH, GP, AMBH and LCZH where R² > 0.999 and 100.18, 99.92, 100.26 and 100.22% respectively. Therefore, the reported method is selective, specific, precise and accurate for the analyses of different constituents in drug substance and pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords : RP-HPLC, counter cough formulation, gradient elution, validation characteristics.

Introduction

Multi-component formulations have gained a lot of importance due to greater patient acceptability, increased potency, multiple action, fewer side effects and quicker relief. Challenges involved in analysis of these multicomponent formulations are therefore gaining attention of analytical chemists. Present work deals with the simultaneous determination of phenylephrine hydrochloride (PEH), guaiphenesin (GP), ambroxol hydrochloride (AMBH) and levocetirizine dihydrochloride (LCZH). These compounds are commonly used in anticough formulation as strong expectorant (GP and AMBH), as an alpha-adrenergic receptor agonist (PEH) and as a third generation non-sedative antihistamine (LCZH)¹.

Several methods are reported in the literature proposing different analytical techniques to separate similar formulations viz. derivative ultraviolet spectrophotometry^{2,3},

gas chromatography⁴, capillary electrophoresis⁵, HPLC⁶⁻¹¹ and LCMS¹². Pharmacopoeial HPLC methods reported for individual drug are inappropriate for their simultaneous determination because of interferences due to corresponding chromatographic peaks^{13,14}. Existing methods for the determination of combined dosage forms are either complicated or required separation of active ingredients before analysis by UV. HPLC methods^{10,11} with two or three component formulations are more common than those with four or more ingredients^{15,16}. In present investigation a new HPLC method using gradient elution has been developed for the simultaneous determination of PEH, GP, AMBH and LCZH in recently introduced cough-cold formulation. The method is validated as per ICH guidelines¹⁷.

The chemical structures of PEH, GP, LCZH and AMBH are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The chemical structures of compounds (A) phenylephrine hydrochloride, (B) guaiphenesin, (C) levocetirizine hydrochloride and (D) ambroxol hydrochloride present in formulation.

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals :

Reference standards were received as a gift sample from Roorkee Research and Analytical Labs Pvt. Ltd., Roorkee. Solvents employed were of HPLC grade while the chemicals were of analytical grade (Qualigens India, Mumbai). Commercial formulation viz. Viscodyne syrup containing PEH, GP, AMBH and LCZH manufactured in India by Wockhardt Ltd. was purchased from local market.

Preparation of mobile phase :

Mobile phase was obtained from A (phosphate buffer 10 mM, pH 3.0 adjusted by ortho-phosphoric acid) and B (solvent mixture of methanol and acetonitrile in the ratio of 1 : 2) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The optimum multi-linear gradient system

Time (min)	Mobile phase : conc. (%)		Wavelength (nm)
	A	B	
0	95	5	230
8	40	60	230
15	30	70	230
18	95	5	273
30	95	5	273

HPLC apparatus and chromatographic conditions :

A gradient HPLC system (Shimadzu, Prominence model) equipped with LC Solutions software for data processing with LC-20AT double reciprocating pump, SPD-20A UV-Vis detector and RP-C₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm

i.d., 5 µm particle size) Phenomenex, USA column was used. Mobile phase was filtered before use through a 0.45 µm membrane filter to degass and pumped from the respective solvent reservoirs to the column at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The run time was set at 30 min and column temperature was 40 ± 1 °C.

Standard preparation :

Approximately 50 mg of PEH, 500 mg of GP, 150 mg of AMBH and 8 mg of LCZ reference standards were accurately weighed and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. The weighed sample was dissolved in diluent, prepared by mixing methanol and water in the ratio of 20 : 80, sonicated for 10 min and made up to volume with diluent to produce a stock solution. Aliquots of the stock solution were diluted to produce dilutions of suitable concentration. Each of the drug solution was filtered through a membrane filter of 0.45 µm, injected (20 µl) in triplicate into the column and the peak area and retention time were recorded. The average value of the peak area was used for calculations after ensuring that the RSD was < 2% (n = 6).

Sample preparation :

Using volumetric pipette of grade A, 5 ml sample of commercial formulation containing label claim of PEH 5 mg, GP 50 mg, AMBH 15 mg and LCZH 0.8 mg were taken accurately in a 100 ml volumetric flask. To recover left over sample from pipette, it was rinsed three times with diluent, and this diluent was collected in same volumetric flask sonicated for 10 min and made up to volume with diluent.

Results and discussion

To develop a new HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of phenylephrine hydrochloride, guaiphenesin, ambroxol hydrochloride and levocetirizine dihydrochloride in its pharmaceutical dosage form, detection wavelength, solvent systems and their compositions were explored. Mobile phase consisting of A (phosphate buffer 10 mM, pH 3.0 adjusted by ortho-phosphoric acid) and B (solvent mixture of methanol and acetonitrile in the ratio of 1 : 2) was found to furnish sharp, well-defined and well resolved peaks in a good symmetry. Systematic variation of their ratio together with detection wavelength resulted in separation of peaks. Detection wavelength of 273 nm (GP and PEH) and 230 nm (AMBH and LCZH) and the mobile phase of buffer and solvent mixture using gradient system were given in Table 1 were finalized. After initial efforts with isocratic elution, gradient elution was preferred to determine above four components simultaneously. Developed method is highly selective, specific and suitable with simple types of columns. System suitability tests were performed as shown in Table 2. The retention times for AMBH, LCZH, GP and PEH under the optimized chromatographic con-

Fig. 2. Showing separated peaks of ambroxol (RT - 9.23 min), levocetirizine (RT - 15.10 min), guaiphenesin (RT -19.54 min) and phenylephrine (RT - 25.36 min).

Table 2. System suitability

Parameter	Ambroxol	Levocetirizine	Guaiphenesin	Phenylephrine
Retention time (min)	9.23	15.10	19.54	25.36
Resolution (R_s)	-	13.35	9.87	8.725
Selectivity (α)	-	1.54	1.29	1.18
Tailing factor	1.04	1.13	0.85	1.01

ditions was found to be 9.23 min, 15.10 min, 19.54 min and 25.36 min respectively (Fig. 2). Prior to implementation for the quantitative determination of drug substances and pharmaceutical preparation, this method was thoroughly validated¹⁷ for its linearity, specificity, accuracy, inter and intra-day precision.

Linearity and range :

The calibration curve was generated from five concentration levels of 25-125 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for PEH, 250-1250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for GP, 75-375 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for AMBH and 4-20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for LCZH and the corresponding peak areas. The method was linear in the given range (Table 3) and calibration curve could be described by the equation $y = ax + b$. The correlation coefficient (Table 4) for these compounds ($R_2 > 0.999$) suggests that method provides good linear dynamic range.

ml^{-1} for LCZH and the corresponding peak areas. The method was linear in the given range (Table 3) and calibration curve could be described by the equation $y = ax + b$. The correlation coefficient (Table 4) for these compounds ($R_2 > 0.999$) suggests that method provides good linear dynamic range.

Table 3. Range

Compound name	Lower range (50% level)		Higher range (150% level)	
	Mean recovery	RSD (%)	Mean recovery	RSD (%)
Phenylephrine HCl	101.20	0.56	100.13	0.29
Guaiphenesin	99.96	0.79	99.91	0.81
Ambroxol hydrochloride	101.07	0.81	100.04	1.02
Levocetirizine dihydrochloride	101.00	0.59	100.08	0.88

Table 4. Linearity

Compound name	Multiple R	R Square	Standard error
Phenylephrine HCl	0.999699	0.999398	62894.98
Guaiphenesin	0.999995	0.99999	141466.4
Ambroxol HCl	0.999629	0.999258	81204.58
Levocetirizine di HCl	0.999995	0.99999	1815.054

Accuracy :

Accuracy test was done by performing assay of components calculated from peak area responses of different samples by analyte recovery and standard addition method.

Analyte recovery method :

Into blank syrup matrix, all components were spiked from a standard stock solution with 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150% of the target level in the syrup. Each of the spiked solution was injected in triplicate. Mean recovery and RSD have been shown in Table 5.

Intermediate precision was performed by analyzing samples by two different analysts using different instruments. Standard solution and ten different samples at 100% target level were prepared by each analyst. Relative standard deviations obtained from 20 assay results by two analysts for six days were 0.638% for PEH, 1.107% for GP, 1.193% for AMBH and 1.607% for LCZH.

Table 5. Recovery of analytes

Phenylephrine hydrochloride							
Theoretical % of target level	50	75	100	125	150	Mean	RSD (%)
Recovery (%)	101.20	101.07	98.80	99.68	100.13	100.18	0.99
Bias	1.20	1.07	-1.20	-0.32	0.13		
Guaiphenesin							
Theoretical % of target level	50	75	100	125	150	Mean	RSD (%)
Recovery (%)	99.96	100.48	99.46	99.81	99.91	99.92	0.37
Bias	0.04	0.48	-0.54	-0.19	-0.09		
Ambroxol hydrochloride							
Theoretical % of target level	50	75	100	125	150	Mean	RSD (%)
Recovery (%)	101.07	100.62	99.67	99.89	100.04	100.26	0.57
Bias	1.07	0.62	-0.37	-0.11	0.04		
Levocetirizine dihydrochloride							
Theoretical % of target level	50	75	100	125	150	Mean	RSD (%)
Recovery (%)	101.00	100.83	99.50	99.70	100.08	100.22	0.67
Bias	1.00	0.83	-0.50	-0.30	0.18		

Standard addition method :

Accuracy was also determined by standard addition method with the help of spiked matrix solution at concentration level of 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150% of label claim, thus making overall concentration 150, 175, 200, 225 and 250% respectively. Each of spiked samples was analyzed and measured amounts were compared with total theoretical amount present. Mean recovery was 100.65% for PEH, 99.26% for GP, 101.09% for AMBH and 101.16% for LCZH.

Precision :

Method precision or intra-assay precision was performed by preparing six different standard solutions. Each solution was injected in triplicate under same conditions and mean value of peak area response for each solution taken. Relative standard deviations were 0.839% for PEH, 0.761% for GP, 0.427% for AMBH and 1.625% for LCZH.

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